

Benchmarking the Poseidon and Rescue-Prime Permutations Using a Shared Halo2 Circuit Construction

Declan Murphy

Abstract—As zero-knowledge proof systems become increasingly prevalent, there is a need for arithmetic hash functions that operate efficiently over finite fields. Unlike hash functions that use bitwise operations, such as SHA-256, arithmetic hash functions use native field operations. When expressed as circuits over finite fields of large prime order, these arithmetic designs result in comparatively lower circuit complexity. Two prevalent examples of arithmetic hash functions are Poseidon and Rescue-Prime.

In this work, we create Halo2 circuits for the Poseidon and Rescue-Prime permutations, derived from a shared circuit construction. We benchmark the resulting circuits and report low-level circuit metrics. Our comparative analysis highlights both the differences between the permutations and their tradeoffs in the context of Halo2 circuits. The shared circuit construction is also contributed as a controlled methodology for benchmarking permutations in Halo2 circuits.

I. INTRODUCTION

Zero-knowledge proof systems, such as Halo2, express computations as arithmetic circuits over large prime fields. In this setting, the design of the hash function has a significant impact on circuit performance. Arithmetic hash functions, designed to be implemented in zero-knowledge proof systems, use native field operations. This results in comparatively lower circuit complexity and arithmetization cost compared to non-arithmetic hash functions. That said, the cost of arithmetization is not the only factor influencing circuit performance.

Poseidon and Rescue-Prime are two prominent arithmetic hash functions, designed for use in zero-knowledge proving systems [GKR⁺19], [SAD20]. While Poseidon and Rescue-Prime share certain structure and functionality, their designs differ in the round structure and non-linear layers. Under the Hades construction, Poseidon uses both full and partial rounds. This combination of full and partial rounds reduces computation in the non-linear layer, without loss of security [GLR⁺19]. On the other hand, Rescue-Prime uses a power map and its inverse as the non-linear transformations. Because Rescue-Prime does not use the Hades construction, these transformations are uniformly applied in every round. These design differences result in diverging circuit constructions and thus different low-level circuit metrics.

In this work, we create Halo2 circuits for the Poseidon and Rescue-Prime permutations, derived from a shared circuit construction. We benchmark the circuits and report low-level metrics for the rows, cells, gates, and constraints. We then analyze the metrics comparatively and identify tradeoffs that arise from design differences between the permutations.

A. Our contributions

We implement a shared Halo2 circuit construction for the Poseidon and Rescue-Prime hash permutations: POSEIDON^π and Rescue-XLIX. The common circuit construction captures functional similarities between the permutations, such as matrix-vector multiplication and round constant addition. These common functional design elements are implemented as gates, constraints, and selectors in the shared circuit construction. To maximize consistency across the two circuits, parameters such as state size, security level, and underlying field are also fixed in the shared circuit construction. Where the permutations deviate, the circuit constructions diverge accordingly. This results in two distinct circuits, built from the same skeleton.

Additionally, we contribute the shared circuit construction and associated metrics as a controlled methodology for benchmarking arithmetic permutations using Halo2. Our methodology demonstrates how to control confounding variables when benchmarking multiple permutations under Halo2’s PLONK-ish arithmetization. This control ensures the low-level circuit metrics accurately reflect permutation design, eliminating non-insightful overhead and configuration bias.

Because this work focuses on the different state transformations and the round structures, the implemented Halo2 circuits only perform the internal hash permutations. Removing the padding and sponge input/output (I/O) operations reduces non-insightful overhead. Importantly, because the POSEIDON^π and Rescue-XLIX permutations are independent of padding and sponge I/O operations, excluding these components does not bias the circuit-level metrics.

This work does not introduce new cryptographic constructions or security results. Its contribution is an empirical evaluation and comparative analysis of existing arithmetic hash permutations within a shared Halo2 circuit construction. Because this work is intended solely for benchmarking, the code is not designed for a production deployment.

II. PRELIMINARIES

A. Poseidon

The Poseidon hash function instantiates a sponge construction with the POSEIDON^π permutation. The hash function computes the mapping $\mathbb{F}_p^* \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_p^o$, sending an arbitrary number of field elements to o output elements. Within this mapping, the POSEIDON^π permutation performs the round-based manipulation of the state elements: $F_p^m \rightarrow F_p^m$. Given the rate

r and the capacity c , POSEIDON $^\pi$ has an internal state of $m = r + c$ field elements [GKR⁺19].

1) *The POSEIDON $^\pi$ permutation*: Under the Hades construction, POSEIDON $^\pi$ uses four sub-functions: AddRoundConstants (ARC), full SubWords (SB_{full}), partial SubWords (SB_{partial}), and MixLayer (ML), with the following functionality [GKR⁺19]:

- ARC: Add the next m round constants to the state elements.
- SB_{full}: Apply the power map $(\cdot)^\alpha$ to all state elements. Because α and $(p - 1)$ are coprime, the power map is a bijection over \mathbb{F}_p . This sub-function is used as the non-linear transformation in the R_F full rounds.
- SB_{partial}: Apply the power map $(\cdot)^\alpha$ to the first state element only. This sub-function is used as the non-linear transformation in the R_P partial rounds.
- ML: Perform matrix-vector multiplication with an $m \times m$ MDS matrix (see [MS78] for details) and the state vector. This linear layer provides maximum diffusion while preserving bijectivity.

POSEIDON $^\pi$ runs ARC, either SB_{full} or SB_{partial}, and ML in each round. Since each sub-function is a bijection over \mathbb{F}_p^m , the mapping POSEIDON $^\pi$: $\mathbb{F}_p^m \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_p^m$ is a permutation over the state space.

2) *POSEIDON $^\pi$ parameter selection*: This work adopts parameters from poseidonperm_x5_255_3, a reference implementation for POSEIDON $^\pi$. The reference implementation targets a security level of $M = 128$ bits. This security level corresponds to a 255-bit capacity, or one field element when instantiated over BLS12-381 [GKR⁺19]. The parameters used are presented in the list below [rc21]:

- Field: BLS12-381
- m : 3
- R_F : 8
- R_P : 57
- α : 5

We verify that the parameters from the reference implementation satisfy the necessary conditions for POSEIDON $^\pi$. For SB_{full} and SB_{partial} we ensure the exponent α is the smallest integer satisfying $\alpha \geq 3$ and $\text{GCD}(\alpha, (p - 1)) = 1$. To verify parameters for ARC, the number of round constants in the reference implementation is checked against $m * (R_F + R_P)$ [rc21] [GKR⁺19].

For reproducibility and verification, the MDS matrix is provided in Appendix A. The first three and final round constants are also provided in Appendix B.

3) *The Hades construction*: The Hades construction uses a mix of full and partial rounds. This use of R_F full rounds and R_P partial rounds reduces computation in the non-linear layer, without reducing the security level. Assuming R_F is even, the Hades construction performs $R_F/2$ full rounds, R_P partial rounds, then the remaining $R_F/2$ full rounds. This scheme masks partial rounds with full rounds, preventing attackers from directly taking advantage of rounds with a partial non-linear transformation [GLR⁺19]. The reference implementation computes partial rounds by applying the power map to the first state element only [rc21]. We implement this construction using the SB_{partial} and SB_{full} sub-functions.

B. Rescue-Prime

The Rescue-Prime hash function instantiates a sponge construction with a rate r and a capacity c . The hash function computes the mapping $\mathbb{F}_p^* \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_p^r$, sending arbitrarily long sequences of field elements to r output elements. Within this mapping, Rescue-Prime uses the Rescue-XLIX permutation. Rescue-XLIX computes the mapping $\mathbb{F}_p^m \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_p^m$ with an internal state of $m = r + c$ field elements [SAD20].

1) *The Rescue-XLIX permutation*: Rescue-XLIX uses four sub-functions: a power map (SB), MDS multiplication (ML), round constant injection (ARC), and an inverse power map (SB_INV).¹ These sub-functions perform the following functionality [SAD20]:

- SB: apply the power map $(\cdot)^\alpha$ to each state element.
- ML: perform matrix-vector multiplication with the state vector and an $m \times m$ MDS matrix.
- ARC: add the next m round constants to the state elements. The constants are stored in a list $\{C_i\}_{i=0}^{2mN-1}$ where N is the number of rounds.
- SB_INV: apply the inverse power map $(\cdot)^{\alpha^{-1}}$ to each state element.

Rescue-XLIX runs N rounds, each performing the following sub-functions: SB, ML, ARC, SB_INV, ML, ARC [SAD20]. Because each sub-function is a bijection over \mathbb{F}_p^m , Rescue-XLIX is a permutation over the state space.

2) *Rescue-XLIX parameter selection*: The Rescue-Prime specification provides code for generating parameters. To work with a shared circuit construction, we adapt the given code to generate Rescue-XLIX parameters for BLS12-381, with $s = 128$ bits of security. The parameters used are presented in the list below: [SAD20].

- Field: BLS12-381
- m : 3
- N : 14
- α : 5
- α^{-1} : 0x2e5f0fbadd72321ce14a56699d73f0022
17f0e679998f19933333332ccccccc

The parameters above are selected according to the Rescue-Prime specification. For SB we choose the minimal $\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}$; $\alpha \geq 3$ such that $\text{GCD}(\alpha, p - 1) = 1$. This allows us to calculate α^{-1} as the modular multiplicative inverse of α in BLS12-381. Round constants for ARC are generated by using SHAKE-256 to expand the string "Rescue-XLIX(p, m, c, s).". To generate the MDS matrix, we fix a primitive element $g = 7$, ensuring its powers generate the full multiplicative group of \mathbb{F}_p . After fixing a primitive element of BLS12-381, we follow the MDS generation process, ensuring the output takes the form $[I_3 | MDS]$ [SAD20].

For reproducibility and verification, the MDS matrix is provided in Appendix C. The first three and final round constants are also provided in Appendix D.

C. The Halo2 proving system

We use the Halo2 proving system to implement PLONKish circuits for both POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX. In the Halo2

¹We use the same acronym for functionally equivalent sub-functions between Rescue-XLIX and POSEIDON $^\pi$ for consistency.

proving system, circuits run over a layout of columns and rows. Each variable is assigned to a column, and each row represents one iteration of the circuit’s execution trace. A cell, therefore, holds the value of a variable at a given iteration of the execution. Halo2 uses several types of columns, each serving a different purpose. Advice columns store private inputs, known only by the prover. Fixed columns hold constant values that do not change between proofs, known by both the prover and the verifier. Finally, instance columns hold public inputs or outputs, known by both the prover and verifier [kha26]. To perform the manipulation of variables, custom gates are configured in the circuit’s chip(s). At a given row, a gate is either active or inactive depending on the value of its associated selector. An active selector is set to 1, while an inactive selector is set to 0. To prove that the computation was performed correctly, each gate is configured with a set of user-defined constraints, which must each evaluate to zero. This support for custom gates and constraints enables the arithmetization of non-trivial functionality [TECC22].

We use custom gates and constraints to create the shared circuit construction. Distinct chips for POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX extend this construction to form complete circuits.

III. SHARED CIRCUIT CONSTRUCTION

The goal of the shared circuit construction is to minimize structural variation between the POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX circuits. Reducing unnecessary variation ensures any performance difference is the result of design differences between the permutations, rather than configuration choices. In this shared circuit construction, both POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX use a single chip, configured with the same number of columns. Where POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX overlap, such as in the linear layer, the same helper function is used to create the corresponding gate and constraints. The list below presents the common elements captured by the shared circuit construction for the POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX circuits:

- Advice columns: 3
- Fixed columns: 3
- Instance columns: 1
- ML gate and constraints
- ARC gate and constraints
- Chips per permutation: 1
- Total rows: 2^k with $k = 10$

Using different state sizes for each permutation would result in a different number of constraints, for otherwise equivalent sub-operations. Similarly, using a different underlying field would result in different arithmetization costs. Thus, we fix BLS12-381 as the underlying field and $m = 3$ for both permutations. These common parameters facilitate shared helper functions for gate construction, shared constraints, and identical column configurations. Each permutation’s chip is configured with m advice columns and m fixed columns. The advice columns hold the m state elements, and each fixed column stores the round constants added to one of the state elements. We use m fixed columns so that the ARC gate can

access the needed constants at a single rotation. The singular instance column is used to expose the final state elements as the public output.

The following sections explain how each permutation extends the shared circuit construction to implement its full functionality.

A. POSEIDON $^\pi$ deviations

The POSEIDON $^\pi$ permutation introduces the non-linear layer, Hades construction, and POSEIDON $^\pi$ specific parameters to the shared circuit construction. The list below presents the POSEIDON $^\pi$ specific circuit elements:

- SB_{full} gate and constraints
- SB_{partial} gate and constraints
- Hades construction using R_F and R_P

B. Rescue-XLIX deviations

The Rescue-XLIX permutation introduces the non-linear layers, round structure, and Rescue-XLIX specific parameters to the shared circuit construction. The list below presents the Rescue-XLIX specific circuit elements:

- SB gate and constraints
- SB_INV gate and constraints
- Rescue-XLIX round structure

Since $\alpha = 5$ is used for SB_{full} in POSEIDON $^\pi$ and SB in Rescue-XLIX, these sub-functions are functionally equivalent. That said, these sub-functions serve different purposes within each permutation. SB_{full} is used as the entire non-linear layer in POSEIDON $^\pi$ full rounds. On the other hand, Rescue-XLIX uses SB and SB_INV for the non-linear transformations. We use distinct, but functionally equivalent, helper functions to construct identical gates and constraints for SB_{full} and SB. This approach allows us to preserve conceptual differences within the circuit, and respect design differences in the permutations.

C. Arithmetization

Under the shared circuit construction, both circuits share the same tuple of columns [kha26]:

$$(\text{adv}_0, \text{adv}_1, \text{adv}_2, \text{fix}_0, \text{fix}_1, \text{fix}_2, s_{\text{ARC}}, s_{\text{ML}}, s_{\text{SB}}, s_{\text{SB}'})$$

At some row i , we denote the tuple values as:

$$(x_a^i, x_b^i, x_c^i, f_a^i, f_b^i, f_c^i, s_{\text{ARC}}^i, s_{\text{ML}}^i, s_{\text{SB}}^i, s_{\text{SB}'}^i)$$

Since each permutation uses two distinct gates for the non-linear layer, we denote the second selector needed as $s_{\text{SB}'}$. Given n rows, the Halo2 proving system uses the powers of an n th root of unity to form an evaluation domain. Lagrange polynomials, of degree $n - 1$, are constructed for each column. These Lagrange polynomials interpolate between points in the evaluation domain and the column-assigned values [TECC22]. Under this PLONKish arithmetization, fixing the column tuple in the shared circuit construction maximizes arithmetic consistency across both circuits. This ensures that differences in constraint structure and circuit metrics arise from permutation design choices rather than from column configuration.

TABLE I
CIRCUIT LAYOUT METRICS FOR POSEIDON $^\pi$ AND RESCUE-XLIX

Layout Metrics	Rows Used	Advice Cells	Fixed Cells	Total Cells
POSEIDON $^\pi$	196	588	195	786
Rescue-XLIX	85	255	84	342

IV. BENCHMARKS AND RESULTS

We use the Mock prover to run both Halo2 circuits, with benchmarking instrumentation embedded in each circuit’s chip synthesis. This section reports the following metrics for both circuits:

- Number of rows used
- Number of advice cells used
- Number of fixed cells used
- Total cells used
- Number of activated gates
- Total constraints
- Maximum constraint degree
- Mock prover runtime over 30 iterations

A. Hardware and software used

To enable reproducibility and add context, this section documents the hardware and software used:

- CPU: 12th Gen Intel i9-12900H
- GPU: NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 Ti Laptop GPU
- Memory: 15825MiB
- OS: Ubuntu 22.04.4 (in WSL2)
- rustc version: 1.87.0
- Kernel: x86_64 Linux 6.6.87.2-microsoft-standard-WSL2
- halo2_proofs: 0.3.1
- halo2curves: 0.9.0
- num-bigint: 0.4

B. Circuit layout metrics

To accurately measure the circuit layout metrics, we instrument the chip synthesis phases with counters. These counters are incremented accordingly as the permutation runs. We present circuit layout metrics for POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX in Table I.

The total cell counts are calculated as `advice_cells + fixed_cells + 3`. We add 3 cells to account for the instance cells used for exposing the final state elements as public output. Because the sponge I/O and padding operations are not in-scope, the final state elements are treated as the public output.

C. Gate and constraint metrics

We present gate and constraint metrics for POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX in Table II. The number of activated gates is calculated by incrementing a counter whenever a selector is enabled. An inactive selector holds a value of 0, automatically forcing the associated constraint(s) to evaluate to 0.

The total number of constraints refers to the number of vector elements returned by all gates in the circuit. Each vector

TABLE II
GATE AND CONSTRAINT METRICS FOR POSEIDON $^\pi$ AND RESCUE-XLIX

Gate/Constraint Metrics	Activated Gates	Total Constraints	Maximum Degree
POSEIDON $^\pi$	195	13	6
Rescue-XLIX	84	15	6

Fig. 1. Mock prover runtimes for POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX over 30 executions.

element corresponds to a different constraint polynomial, even if multiple constraints have the same algebraic form. On top of these gate constraints, each circuit has $m = 3$ copy constraints for exposing the final state elements as public.

The maximum constraint degrees are calculated by expressing each constraint as a polynomial and taking the maximum number of multiplied values. With both POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX, the maximum degree constraint comes from the non-linear layer.

Let $S_{SB}(X)$ denote the selector polynomial for either SB_{full} in POSEIDON $^\pi$ or SB in Rescue-XLIX. Let $A_j(X)$ denote the advice polynomial for the j th state element with $j \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. Given $\alpha = 5$, the constraint polynomials in the non-linear layer have the same form for both permutations:

$$P_j^{SB}(X) = S_{SB}(X)(A_j(X+1) - A_j(X)^5)$$

For Rescue-XLIX, despite $\alpha^{-1} > \alpha$, the SB_INV gate uses a constraint polynomial of the same degree as SB . To avoid calculating $A_j(X)^{\alpha^{-1}}$, we constrain the relationship between $A_j(X)$ and $A_j(X+1)$ instead of the values themselves. Thus, the constraint polynomials for SB_INV have the same degree as SB :

$$P_j^{SB_INV}(X) = S_{SB_INV}(X)(A_j(X) - A_j(X+1)^5)$$

D. Mock prover runtimes

We run the Halo2 Mock prover for $n = 30$ iterations on both circuits. We measure the time the Mock prover takes to complete for each iteration and present the results in Figure 1.

V. ANALYSIS

A. Layout metrics analysis

In this analysis, we define a state update as a sub-function that writes manipulated state elements to the next row in the circuit layout. Thus, the total number of state updates is given by the number of sub-function invocations needed by the permutation. In each round POSEIDON $^\pi$ calls ARC, SB_{full} or SB_{partial}, and ML, resulting in 3 state updates per round. On the other hand, Rescue-XLIX calls SB, ML, ARC, SB_INV, ML, and ARC every round, resulting in 6 state updates per round. We denote these values as $u = 3$ for POSEIDON $^\pi$ and $u = 6$ for Rescue-XLIX. We also denote the number of rounds as $n = (R_F + R_P) = 65$ for POSEIDON $^\pi$ and $n = 14$ for Rescue-XLIX.

Because each state update writes to the next row in the layout, we calculate the number of rows used as $u * n + 1$. We add 1 additional row to account for storing the initial state elements in the layout, giving the total counts in Table I. We confirm the intuition that although Rescue-XLIX requires more state updates per-round, the overall number of state updates drives the number of rows used.

Under the shared circuit construction, each permutation's chip is configured with m advice columns. These advice columns store the state elements as they are manipulated throughout the rounds. Given this setup, the number of advice cells used can be calculated as $u * m * n + 3$. We add 3 additional advice cells to account for storing the initial state elements in the m advice columns, giving the total counts reported in Table I. We observe that, under this shared circuit construction, the number of advice cells needed is the product of m and the number of rows used. Thus, the number of advice cells used is directly proportional to the total number of state updates.

The shared circuit construction configures each permutation's chip with m fixed columns to store the round constants needed by the permutation. Each fixed column stores the round constants added to one state element. This column layout allows ARC to access the round constants needed at a single rotation. It follows that the number of fixed cells used is the same as the number of round constants needed by the permutation. This is calculated as the product of m and the number of times ARC is called throughout the permutation, resulting in the fixed cell totals in Table I. This calculation works because ARC uses m round constants for both POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX.

Under the Hades construction, POSEIDON $^\pi$ is able to reduce computations in the non-linear layer. Even though partial rounds only compute the power map for the first state element, all m elements are written to the next row. We could use $(m - 1) * R_P$ less advice cells by not writing unchanged state elements to the next row, but this has several undesirable complications. Namely, the gate and constraints for the subsequent sub-operation, ML, would have to reference multiple rotations to operate on the latest state elements. This complexity would cause the POSEIDON $^\pi$ circuit to unnecessarily deviate from the shared circuit construction. We do not

implement this design to keep the gate and constraints for the linear layer shared between POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX.

The results in Table I show that the circuit layout metrics are primarily a function of the total number of state updates. Based on these results, we observe that POSEIDON $^\pi$ requires 2.3 more rows, advice cells, and fixed cells than Rescue-XLIX. This is consistent with the design of each permutation since POSEIDON $^\pi$ requires 2.3 times as many state updates as Rescue-XLIX. POSEIDON $^\pi$ optimizes computation under the Hades construction, but this optimization does not propagate to the circuit layout metrics. On the other hand, despite requiring more computation per-round, Rescue-XLIX uses less total state updates. This design results in comparatively fewer rows, advice cells, and fixed cells used.

B. Gate and constraint metrics analysis

For each permutation, the number of activated gates is measured by incrementing a counter whenever a selector is enabled. For POSEIDON $^\pi$, the ARC, SB_{full}, ML gates are each enabled once per R_F rounds. For R_P rounds the ARC, SB_{partial}, ML gates are enabled once per round. This design results in 195 gate activations. On the other hand, Rescue-XLIX enables the gates for ARC and ML twice per round, and the gates for SB, SB_INV once per round. This design results in 84 gate activations. These results show that, under the shared circuit construction, the number of activated gates is the same as the number of sub-operation invocations.

The total number of constraints is counted as the number of vector elements returned over all gates in a permutation. The shared circuit construction establishes 6 shared constraints for ARC and ML. An additional 3 copy constraints are used in each permutation for exposing the final state. Both permutations deviate from the shared circuit construction, resulting in different constraint counts due to design differences. The key insight from these results is that POSEIDON $^\pi$ uses less constraints than Rescue-XLIX because the Hades construction only constrains the first state element in the partial rounds.

Because both permutations uses $\alpha = 5$ in the non-linear layer, the maximum constraint degree is the same for both permutations. We avoid exploding the constraint degree for SB_INV by constraining the relationship between rotations instead of the values themselves.

C. Mock prover runtime analysis

Because the Mock prover is subject to OS level anomalies and noise, we report the runtime data strictly for completeness. Figure 1 shows outlier data points for both permutations, which we attribute to OS noise and not to the circuit constructions. The Rescue-XLIX box plot collapses because 28/30 data points equal 14 ms, with 2 upper outliers at 15 and 21 ms. The POSEIDON $^\pi$ box plot reflects an upper outlier at 35 ms, which we attribute to the OS.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work we construct a shared circuit construction for the arithmetic hash permutations POSEIDON $^\pi$ and

Rescue-XLIX. This shared circuit construction captures overlap in these permutations by fixing parameters, gates, constraints, and column structure. Specifically, we fix BLS12-381 as the underlying field, security level, permutation state size, ARC gates and constraints, ML gates and constraints, and column structure for each circuit. Functionality that is specific to POSEIDON $^\pi$ or Rescue-XLIX is added to the shared circuit construction, resulting in two complete circuits derived from the same skeleton. The chip synthesis, for each circuit, is instrumented with counters for benchmarking. The Mock prover is used to perform the computation and provide basic runtime metrics. This controlled methodology ensures that any differences in circuit-level metrics result from design differences between the permutations, not confounding variables.

Under this methodology, we gather low-level circuit metrics such as number of rows, advice cells, gates, and constraints used. We also report maximum constraint degree under Halo2’s PLONKish arithmetization. Given these metrics, our results show that the low-level circuit metrics are a function of the total number of state updates performed by the permutation. Computational optimizations, such as the Hades construction, do not propagate to metrics such as rows and cells used. Rescue-XLIX uses 2.3 times less state updates than POSEIDON $^\pi$, which proportionally drives the circuit layout metrics. For both permutations, the maximum constraint degree comes from the non-linear transformations. We avoid inflating the constraint degree for Rescue-XLIX by constraining computational relationships, as opposed to values.

These results highlight an important distinction between computational efficiency and circuit-level efficiency. Optimizations that reduce arithmetic computation do not necessarily optimize low-level circuit metrics. Computational optimizations that increase the number of state updates create a tradeoff between the computation and circuit metrics. This suggests that circuit structure should be considered alongside computational optimization when considering permutation design.

VII. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work is subject to the following limitations:

- The state size is fixed at $m = 3$; other state sizes were not evaluated.
- The security level of 128 bits is fixed; different security levels were not evaluated.
- Larger evaluation domain than required for both permutations; 2^k with $k = 10$ could be reduced to lower prover overhead.
- Limited prover and verifier performance metrics due to only using the Mock prover.
- Only the permutations are computed; the full hash function, including sponge I/O and padding is not evaluated.
- The scope is limited to POSEIDON $^\pi$ and Rescue-XLIX.

These limitations create possibilities for future circuit engineering and benchmarking work. Evaluating permutations using multiple state sizes, security levels, and proving systems would provide more insight into how hash functions perform in arithmetic circuits. Additionally, future work could apply

this methodology to other hash functions such as Griffin [GHR⁺22]. Finally, this work focuses on the circuit level metrics, but future work could expand into prover and verifier performance as well.

VIII. CODE AVAILABILITY

The code for both circuits, along with testing and parameter generation scripts, is made publicly available at <https://github.com/D3c14n/poseidon-rescue-halo2-benchmarking/tree/main> at release v1.0.1. The repository contains the Halo2 circuit implementations, parameter generation utilities, and benchmarking instrumentation used to produce the results reported in this work [Mur26].

APPENDIX

A. POSEIDON $^\pi$ MDS matrix

The 3×3 MDS matrix used in this work for POSEIDON $^\pi$ is given by the following entries (line-broken for readability):
MDS =

```
[ 0x3d955d6c02fe4d7cb500e12f2b55eff66
  8a7b4386bd27413766713c93f2acfcfcd,
  0x3798866f4e6058035dcf8addb2cf1771f
  ac234bcc8fc05d6676e77e797f224bf,
  0x2c51456a7bf2467eac813649f3f25ea89
  6eac27c5da020dae54a6e640278fda2 ],
[ 0x20088ca07bbcd7490a0218ebc0ecb31d0
  ea34840e2dc2d33a1a5adfecff83b43,
  0x1d04ba0915e7807c968ea4b1cb2d610c7f
  9a16b4033f02ebacbb948c86a988c3,
  0x5387ccd5729d7acbd09d96714d1d18bbd0
  eeafb2dde3d2ef573c9c7f953307 ],
[ 0x1e208f585a72558534281562cad89659b4
  28ec61433293a8d7f0f0e38a6726ac,
  0x0455ebf862f0b60f69698e97d36e8aafd4
  d107cae2b61be1858b23a3363642e0,
  0x569e2c206119e89455852059f707370e2c
  1fc9721f6c50991cedbbf782daef54 ]
```

B. POSEIDON $^\pi$ round constants

ROUND_CONSTANTS =

```
[ 0x6c4ffa723eaf1a7bf74905cc7dae4ca9ff
  4a2c3bc81d42e09540d1f250910880,
  0x54dd837eccf180c92c2f53a3476e45a156
  ab69a403b6b9fd8dd970fddcdd9a,
  0x64f56d735286c35f0e7d0a29680d49d54f
  b924adccf8962eeee225bf9423a85e,
  ...
  0x57b33094aef828377897b56e1c432978d
  07c668ef25a36bc5e2e835aaeff725 ]
```

C. Rescue-XLIX MDS matrix

The 3×3 MDS matrix used in this work for Rescue-XLIX is given by the following entries (line-broken for readability):
MDS =

```

        [ 0x157,
0x73eda753299d7d483339d80809a1d8055
 3bda402fffe5bfefffffffffffffe72,
        0x39 ],
        [ 0x4c5f,
0x73eda753299d7d483339d80809a1d80553
 bda402fffe5bfefffffffffffffa881,
        0xb22 ],
        [ 0xeea8e,
0x73eda753299d7d483339d80809a1d80553
 bda402fffe5bfefffffffffffeef262,
        0x22312 ]

```

D. Rescue-XLIX round constants

ROUND_CONSTANTS =

```

[ 0x4e79ebb1e5a43abef900bd773cdde906e4
  bf3244749cb64424f7db47ba0dda87,
0xa77d6cd6e8b7c2a4a7a9682a13699328bc
 6db0ce8916d7b0cc68935a315c85a,
0x4522c378b92f444fced0e7809fad3aeace
 56c16c50f7d075b2cd6cff25fc3c7b,
        ...
0x22335910ed632e5c9e2d372efd6e6841fb
 5fee114f08d90dc081a5a59445404 ]

```

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